

Understanding Frontline Employment Services

This study is being undertaken by Dr Michael McGann and Dr Mary Murphy from Department of Sociology and MU Social Sciences Institute, Maynooth University. It is part of a research project which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie-Sklodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 841477.

The study is concerned with understanding how public employment services in Ireland are delivered by a range of organisations.

Some employment services are delivered by Intreo, a government-run agency. Others are delivered by private and community organisations, who are contracted by the government to deliver Local Employment Services and Job Path. In some cases, the funding these agencies receive depends on what client-outcomes are produced whereas in others it depends on the quantity and nature of services delivered.

We want to understand the services provided by public and contracted employment services, and the impact of funding models on how agencies work with jobseekers. The findings from the research will be used to make recommendations about how to enhance Ireland's employment services system in the future.

What will the study involve?

- Taking part in an anonymous online survey, which should take about 30 minutes.
- **Participants who complete the survey will be entered into a draw to win one of three Dunnes Stores gift certificates worth €500, €300, and €200 respectively.**

To take part, please first read the information sheet about how your data will be used, and your privacy protected.

- You can do so by [clicking here](#)
- Or visiting https://static.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/media/account/253/survey/559046/question/Understanding_Frontline_Employ_q64aue6.pdf.

Then please complete the consent form on the next screen, by selecting 'next' to continue.

Please confirm your agreement to participate in Dr McGann and Dr Murphy’s research study titled ‘Governing Activation in Ireland’ by confirming the statements below:

	Confirm
I have read and understood the information sheet explaining the purpose and nature of the study, and a copy is available for me to download	<input type="radio"/>
I am participating voluntarily.	<input type="radio"/>
I give permission for my survey responses to be stored in a database in anonymised form	<input type="radio"/>
I understand that I can withdraw from the study, without repercussions, at any time up until I reach the end of the survey (by closing the browser or selecting the option to exit the survey). However, once I have completed the survey it will not be possible to withdraw my data because of its anonymous nature.	<input type="radio"/>
It has been explained to me how my data will be managed	<input type="radio"/>
I understand the limits of confidentiality as described in the information sheet	<input type="radio"/>
I understand that my data, in an anonymous format, may be used in any subsequent publications and future research projects	<input type="radio"/>
I agree for my data, once anonymised, to be retained indefinitely in the Irish Social Science Data Archive for potential re-use by other researchers.	<input type="radio"/>

If during your participation in this study you feel the information and guidelines that you were given have been neglected or disregarded in any way, or if you are unhappy about the process, please contact the Secretary of the Maynooth University Ethics Committee at research.ethics@mu.ie or +353 (0)1 708 6019. Please be assured that your concerns will be dealt with in a sensitive manner.

For your information the Data Controller for this research project is Maynooth University, Maynooth, Co. Kildare. Maynooth University Data Protection officer is Ann McKeon in Humanity house, room 17, who can be contacted at ann.mckeon@mu.ie. Maynooth University Data Privacy policies can be found at <https://www.maynoothuniversity.ie/data-protection>.

Is it your job (at least in part) to **work directly with jobseekers** to find employment? * *Required*

Yes

No

Which of the following **employment services or programmes** do you mainly deliver in your job? * *Required*

- Intreo
- Job Path
- Local Employment Services
- I do not deliver any of these services of programmes

Please chose one of options above

Are you **DIRECTLY EMPLOYED** by Seetec or Turas Nua, or do you work for an organisation that is **SUBCONTRACTED** by one of these organisations?

- I am directly employed by Seetec or Turas Nus
- I work for an organisation that is a supply chain partner of Seetec or Turas Nua
- I don't know

Is the agency you work for?

- A for-profit company
- A not-for-profit organisation (e.g. charity-owned or a co-op)
- Part of the public service (e.g. Intreo)
- I don't know
- Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

What is your JOB?

- I'm an employment advisor, guidance officer/mediator, or case officer - my job includes working with jobseekers to help them become job ready and/or find employment
- I'm a trainer - my job includes conducting training courses to assist jobseekers become job ready and/or find employment)
- I'm an employer liason/broker, reverse marketer, or business development officer - my job includes working with employers to identify suitable jobs for jobseekers and/or assist jobseekers prepare to meet with suitable employers
- I'm a receptionist - my job includes working with jobseekers when they telephone or arrive at the centre and referring them to the most appropriate case officer
- I manage an employment service or Intreo office - my job includes managing the office staff, but I also work directly with jobseekers at times)
- I'm an information officer
- Other

Please select one of the above options that best describes your role.

If you selected Other, please specify:

Do you work FULL-TIME or PART-TIME?

- Full-time
- Part-time

YOUR BACKGROUND & EXPERIENCE

What is your GENDER?

- Female
- Male
- I do not identify as male or female
- I would prefer not to say
- Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

What AGE GROUP are you in?

- 24 years or under
- 25 to 34 years
- 35 to 44 years
- 45 to 54 years
- 55 years or over

What is the highest level of education that you have completed?

- Primary (no formal secondary education)
- Lower secondary (e.g. Junior, Inter or Group Certificate)
- Upper secondary (e.g. Leaving Certificate or equivalent)
- Third level non-degree (e.g. an apprenticeship, certificate or diploma course)
- Degree Level (e.g. an undergraduate or bachelor's degree)
- A Postgraduate degree
- Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

Before employment services, what industry did you last work in?

- This is the first industry that I have worked in
- Accommodation and food services
- Administrative and support service activities
- Health and social work activities
- Public administration, defence, or compulsory social security
- Education
- Personal Services (eg. Hairdressing, Beautician)
- Wholesale and retail trade
- Agriculture, forestry and fishing
- Manufacturing
- Utilities (e.g. electricity, gas, water, waste management)
- Construction
- Transportation and storage
- Information and Communication
- Financial and insurance activities
- Real estate activities
- Professional, scientific and technical activities
- Arts, entertainment and recreation
- Other industry (not listed)

Please select the most relevant option.

If you selected Other, please specify:

How many years have you worked in the welfare or employment services SECTOR?

- Less than 1 year
- 1 - 5 years
- More than 5 years

How long have you worked for your current employer?

- Less than 1 year
- 1 - 5 years
- More than 5 years

Are you a member of a TRADE UNION?

- Yes
- No

	1. Very	2. Quite	3. Somewhat	4. Neither	5. Not that much	6. Not a lot	7. Not at all
To what extent are you WILLING to exert considerable extra effort on behalf of your organisation?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
To what extent are you SATISFIED with your present conditions of work (pay, hours, promotion etc.)?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				

Please answer on a scale from 1. Very to 7. Not at all

In an average week, what proportion (%) of your time do you spend on each of the following?

	%
In direct contract with clients	<input type="text"/>
Working with other service providers (eg. addiction, housing, or other community services)	<input type="text"/>
Working with employers	<input type="text"/>
On contract compliance to meet government reporting/admin requirements	<input type="text"/>
On internal staff meetings	<input type="text"/>
On other tasks	<input type="text"/>

Please give your best estimate

EXCLUDING contacts associated with assisting a job seeker to obtain an interview, how often would you have any other form of contact (including telephone) with the following?

	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Quarterly	Less than Quarterly	Never
Another office owned by the organisation you work for	<input type="radio"/>					
Another organisation within an area-based or local partnership	<input type="radio"/>					
Officials from an Irish government department	<input type="radio"/>					
Local councils	<input type="radio"/>					
Other welfare or social service providers	<input type="radio"/>					
Employers	<input type="radio"/>					
Training providers	<input type="radio"/>					
Another employment agency	<input type="radio"/>					

ABOUT YOUR CASELOAD

Only including activation clients, what would you estimate your current CASELOAD to be? *Please give the total number of activation clients on your caseload:*

Please enter a whole number (integer).

Do you also work with NON-ACTIVATION CLIENTS (ie. clients who participate on a voluntary basis/are on a payment not subject to mutual commitments)?

Yes

No

How many non-activation clients are on your caseload?

Please enter a whole number (integer).

How many jobseekers would you see in an average day as *individual appointments*?

Please enter a whole number (integer).

What is your best estimate (in percentages) of the number of job seekers you see that are:

	%
Participating in an activity (e.g. a training course, non-vocational programmes, work experience):	<input type="text"/>
Currently looking for employment only and are not participating in any other activity:	<input type="text"/>
Receiving support after being placed in a job or programme:	<input type="text"/>
Not participating in an activity and are currently not looking for work:	<input type="text"/>

In your experience, what are the main issues or barriers affecting the employability of the jobseekers you work with?

Please list up to three main issues in the boxes below	
1:	<input type="text"/>
2:	<input type="text"/>
3:	<input type="text"/>

In your opinion, which is more often to blame if a person is on benefits - lack of effort on their part or circumstances beyond their control?

	1. Lack of effort	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7. Circumstances beyond their control
Answer on a scale from Lack of effort (1) to Circumstances beyond control (7)	<input type="checkbox"/>						

In your opinion, approximately what percentage of people who apply for benefits *would rather be on benefits than work to support themselves and their families?*

The next questions are about how you work with clients, and the tools and approaches that you use in your job when making decisions about what to do with clients.

Do you use the answers to any form of standard CLIENT CLASSIFICATION (profiling) or checklist when deciding how to work with a client or any other course of action?

- Yes
- No

How influential are the following factors in determining what activities are recommended for each client or jobseeker?

	Not at all influential	Somewhat influential	Quite influential	Very influential
Answers to a standard set of assessment questions or sub-questions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My own judgement	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Jobseeker's preference for activities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Labour market demand	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Availability of labour market programme vacancies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Need to substantiate a case for reporting someone for a sanction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Need to get an outcome quickly	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Jobseekers' Probability of Exit (PeX) score	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The government's activation/mutual commitments policy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	1. Very Little	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7. A great deal
To what extent are the decisions you make about your clients determined by STANDARD programme rules and regulations?	<input type="radio"/>						
How much LEEWAY do you have in deciding which program or activity your clients should be assigned to?	<input type="radio"/>						

For the questions above, please select the number that best expresses your view on a scale from 1. Very little to 7. A great deal

	1. A small extent	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7. A large extent
To what extent do you feel that the IT system you use dictates how you do your job?	<input type="radio"/>						

Please give your answer on a scale from 1. Very little to 7. A great deal

HOW MUCH SAY DO YOU ACTUALLY HAVE in making the following work related decisions?

	No say at all	Some say	Moderate say	A good deal of say	A very great deal of say
How you do your JOB	<input type="radio"/>				
How you engage with CLIENTS	<input type="radio"/>				

Agencies must organise their work based on government policy and the nature of the labour market, among other considerations. In the next questions we are interested in your opinion on how these factors impact on your agency and your job.

	1. Strongly Agree	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7. Strongly Disagree
The practice in my agency is to pick out the most capable jobseekers and give them the best service	<input type="radio"/>						

Please answer on a scale from 1. Strongly Agree to 7. Strongly Disagree.

	1. None	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7. A great deal
How much does your agency emphasise giving clients more CHOICE about the services they receive?	<input type="radio"/>						

Please give the number that best expresses your view, from 1. None to 7. A great deal

Based on the practices in your office today, what would you say is the more important goal of your agency: To help clients get jobs as quickly as possible OR to raise education or skills levels of clients so that they can get the job they want in the future.

	1. Get jobs as quickly as possible	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7. Raise education or skill levels
Answer on a scale from 1. To get jobs as quickly as possible to 7. To raise education or skill levels	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

After a short time attending your service, an average jobseeker is offered a low-skill, low-paying job that would make them better off financially. Assume they have two choices: either to TAKE THE JOB and leave welfare OR to stay on benefits and WAIT FOR A BETTER OPPORTUNITY

	1. Take the job and leave welfare	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7. Stay on benefits and wait
If you were asked, what would your PERSONAL ADVICE to this client be?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please answer on a scale from (1) Take the job to (7) Stay on benefits.

Which ONE of the following four statements best describes the thing that determines YOUR work priorities?

- Knowing the RULES and PROCEDURES
- Meeting the TARGETS set by management
- COMPETING successfully with other service providers
- Having the best possible SET OF CONTACTS outside the organisation

Please select one item

The next questions are about monitoring that people are meeting their mutual commitments to look for work, and the role that employment services staff play in monitoring compliance with activation requirements.

Does your office encourage staff not to be lenient or to be lenient in reporting clients for breaching their mutual commitments (e.g. sanctioning)?

	1. Not to be lenient	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7. To be lenient
Answer on a scale from (1) Not to be lenient to (7) To be lenient	<input type="radio"/>						

In a typical two-week period (i.e. pre Covid-19), how many clients would you usually report for breaching their mutual commitments or activation requirements?

Please enter a whole number (integer).

Please give your best estimate of the number of clients.

When would you normally report a client or jobseeker for breaching their mutual commitments or activation requirements? Select either 'Yes' or 'No' for each item:

	YES	NO
My job doesn't involve reporting clients for sanctioning or non-compliance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A jobseeker IS DISMISSED from a job or a training programme	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A jobseeker REFUSES TO APPLY for a suitable job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A jobseeker REFUSES a suitable JOB OFFER	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A jobseeker FAILS TO COMMENCE an employment support programme, work experience, activity or training course	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A jobseeker LEAVES A TRAINING COURSE	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A jobseeker FAILS TO CONTACT our office	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A jobseeker FAILS TO ATTEND a JOB INTERVIEW	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A jobseeker VOLUNTARILY LEAVES A JOB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A jobseeker DOESN'T TURN UP FOR AN APPOINTMENT at our office (e.g. Activation Review Meetings)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A jobseeker FAILS/REFUSES TO SIGN their Personal Progression Plan (PPP) or Record of Mutual Commitment (RMC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A Jobseeker DOES ANY OF THESE FOR A SECOND TIME	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Why might you decide **NOT** to report (for sanctioning) a client who is not meeting their mutual commitments? Please select as many reasons as apply.

- Can't substantiate the case
- Jobseeker agreement (e.g. record of mutual commitment) not specific enough
- Fear for my personal safety
- My reports for non-compliance are often overturned
- Reporting is not an incentive to compliance
- I don't want a reputation for being too tough
- This office does not encourage sanctioning
- The penalties are too harsh on the client
- The jobseeker is normally a good client and I think it would be more effective to issue a verbal warning only
- I disagree with the government's mutual commitments policy
- My job doesn't involve reporting clients for sanctioning or non-compliance

For each item below, please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the statement.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The lines of authority are not clear in my work	<input type="radio"/>				
When it comes to day-to-day work I am free to decide for myself what I will do with each client	<input type="radio"/>				
My supervisor knows a lot about the work I do day-to-day	<input type="radio"/>				
In my job, I am NOT influenced by numerical targets (including performance ratings)	<input type="radio"/>				
The main thing I have to do in this job is gain the trust of the client/jobseeker	<input type="radio"/>				
Our organisation has targets for certain types of clients/jobseekers	<input type="radio"/>				

For each item below, please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the statement.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
When I come across something not covered by the procedural guide, I refer it to my supervisor	<input type="radio"/>				
I use a lot of personal judgement to decide what is best for each client	<input type="radio"/>				
Our computer system tells me what steps to take with clients and when to take them	<input type="radio"/>				
To get jobseekers to pay attention, I often remind them that enforcing compliance is part of my job	<input type="radio"/>				
More and more the objective in this job is to maximise the organisation's financial outcomes	<input type="radio"/>				
I think the objective in this job is to shift the maximum number of jobseekers off benefits	<input type="radio"/>				

For each item, please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the statement.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I consider myself to be an advocate for the clients' rights	<input type="radio"/>				
I use our IT system to track priority clients/job seekers	<input type="radio"/>				
I do tend to take note of those actions with clients that will generate a payable outcome or reach an employment outcome target for the office	<input type="radio"/>				
All my clients receive a similar service	<input type="radio"/>				
I am aware that my organisation pays attention to the income I generate by placing clients	<input type="radio"/>				
In my job, jobseekers are organised into formal and informal priority groups	<input type="radio"/>				

Some people think that there should be more government spending on social security, while other people disagree. For each of the groups below please say whether you agree or disagree that there should be more government spending on benefits for them than now:

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Unemployed people	<input type="radio"/>				
Younger jobseekers	<input type="radio"/>				
Lone parents	<input type="radio"/>				
People with disability who cannot work	<input type="radio"/>				
Carers for people who are sick or disabled	<input type="radio"/>				
Retired people	<input type="radio"/>				

Lastly, in your opinion, what's one measure that could be implemented that would improve the quality of employment services for people on benefits the most?

Thank you for your assistance in completing this survey. Your answers will help us better understand the needs and work of people in this dynamic industry. For your chance to win one of three gift cards valued at €500, €300, and €200, please provide your details below. This contact information WILL NOT be held with the surveys and there will be NO WAY of matching contact information to survey responses.

Also, we may wish to follow-up with some participants about the findings. There is no obligation to take part in any follow-up interview, and this will not affect your eligibility to enter the prize draw. Even if you agree to be contacted, you can still decide not to take part in the interview at a later date.

Prize details

Prize details is closed
